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Financial Analysis of Candlenut Agroforestry System in KPH Dolago Tanggunung Resort Sigi, Central Sulawesi Province, Indonesia

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Abstract

Integrated land use systems, such as agroforestry, were believed to increase opportunities for the sustainability of the agricultural sector and food security. The implementation of agroforestry had an important role in the social and cultural aspects of local communities. This research was conducted at KPH Dolago Tanggunung Resort Sigi. This research was conducted for 6 effective months, from April to October 2018. The main purposes of this research was to analyze the economic value of the business feasibility of the candlenut agroforestry system at KPH Dolago Tanggunung Resort Sigi, to determine the prospects for developing KPH-based Candlenut agroforestry and to analyze the contribution of agroforestry agroforestry systems to food security.

The results shown that all the cultivation of the plants Model I were profitable (feasible) to be cultivated because they had IRR values higher than MAR 5% and Net B / C Ratio higher than 1. Optimum age Model I were reached when the candlenut stands were 20 years old. The average annual increment (MAI) was achieved by Model I of 6.17 m³ / ha / year and the total standing stock volume was 123.31 m³ / ha. The operations of Model shown a positive value of NPV, so it was feasible to continue. The level of resilience Model I could still withstand economic changes with an increase in costs by 10%, or a decrease in income by 10%. The need for the interest rate that could be given so that it was feasible to cultivate Models I was 5% to 89%. The level of income of the community who operated an agroforestry system could improve the welfare and education level of the family. The community empowerment program in the area of the Dolago Tanggunu Resort Palolo KPH working area was still not optimally carried out even though there were existing laws that accommodate it. The candlenut-based agroforestry development model had very high potential to be developed in the KPH Dolago Tanggunu Resort Palolo area, so that it could be used as an agroforestry model for FMU management.

Keywords: *financial, agroforestry, candlenut, KPH Dolago Tanggunung.*

PRELIMINARY

Remarkable success had been achieved by developed countries in the fields of science and technology and had raised their standard of living and quality of life towards a better direction. Nevertheless, poverty was still found in several places, mainly due to limited access to the use of natural resources, including land use (Golar et al., 2019). Thinking was needed to reduce the widening poverty gap, especially in Indonesia (Devi & Uy, 2010).

Integrated land use systems, such as agroforestry, were believed to increase opportunities for the sustainability of the agricultural sector and food security, because agroforestry could provide various ecological and economic benefits (Bergius et al., 2020). This system had contributed to increasing food security, regional and national economies and environmental resilience (Mayrowani & Ashari, 2016a; Supriadi & Pranowo, 2016). However, in general this system had not been studied in depth, especially related to system components and functions in order to overcome policy problems to improve the quality of people's welfare (Golar et al., 2017; Salvati et al., 2015).

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Limited agricultural land encourages farming communities to open new land in forest areas, by cutting trees and dismantling forest plants, and burning plant debris and shrubs, as a result the land becomes critical. In these conditions, the use of degraded land through the development of agroforestry technology becomes very important (Supriadi & Pranowo, 2016).

Mainly, agroforestry development was expected to help optimize the results of a form of sustainable land use to ensure and improve food needs (Tuti Herawati, 2013). Achieving the target of increasing food production could be done with an intensification pattern through improving cultivation technology and extensification, which, among others, could be done through the expansion of agricultural areas in forest lands with the Agroforestry system (Mayrowani & Ashari, 2016a).

The practice of agroforestry had long been practiced by rural communities (local traditional agroforestry), and even in some places the implementation of agroforestry had an important role in the social and cultural aspects of local communities (Sambira et al., 2018). However, studies on land use characteristics (agroforestry-based land use systems and patterns), as well as land use orientation were still rarely studied, especially those on the micro scale (plot-based interactions). This results in limited information on the characteristics of agroforestry at the micro scale.

In the context of food security, the forestry sector had three main functions, namely as a provider of environmental services that enable sustainable food production, a provider of genetic resources that could strengthen food production, and as a provider of land (Salvati et al., 2015; Sambira et al. Through the agroforestry system, forestry land use could be optimized to support the food security program (Tsfaye & Tirivayi, 2020). This could be realized, if the management institution at the site level goes well (Endah Ambarwati et al., 2018a). In this case, the role of Forest Management Units (KPH) was expected to minimize the problem of forest degradation and deforestation, environmental and social problems (Bray, 2015). The application of sustainability principles in FMU development, especially in the context of its operation, had implications for the optimal preservation of forest ecosystems (McGrath et al., 2015). The principles of sustainable FMU development include ecological sustainability, economic sustainability and social sustainability.

The principle of ecological sustainability in FMU development relates to forest management activities in the FMU that still pay attention to the preservation of environmental functions to support the sustainability of the forest ecosystem so as to optimize the socio-economic benefits of the communities around the forest. The principle of economic sustainability in FMU development was related to the sustainability of forestry businesses in the FMU, while still paying attention to ecological and social sustainability, including food security (Maesen & Cadman, 2015).

The use of forests as food providers was also carried out indirectly, namely by utilizing forest areas to produce food sources. Utilization of forest areas, especially in production forest areas, conservation forest area use zones, or buffer zones in protected forest areas; It had been done a lot with the community for the development of other commodities outside the forestry sector, in particular to support the fulfillment of food and medicine, and energy. Agroforestry activities, silvofishery and even plans to use production forest areas that were no longer productive through Silvopastura, were the main alternatives in increasing the contribution of the forestry sector in food supply.

Food supply was the main leading sector developed by the Indonesian government. That was based on a number of considerations. First, Indonesia had natural potential that could be developed as agricultural land. Second, most of the population lives in rural areas whose livelihoods were in the agricultural sector. Third, the need for high technology and science induction designed to develop agriculture without causing damage. Fourth, the availability of abundant agricultural sector labor. Fifth, the threat of food shortages that could be fulfilled independently from domestic products, so that they did not had to depend on foreign agricultural products which one day becomes expensive (Endah Ambarwati et al., 2018b).

Based on the description above, it was important to conduct research on FMU-based agroforestry systems in supporting food security for people living around forests. Besides functioning as a life buffer by maintaining ecological functions, forests could also be used economically in their sustainable and sustainable management.

The main problem examined in this research was how much was the feasibility value of the agroforestry system business carried out by the community around the forest in the KPH Dolago

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Tanggunung Resort Sigi area? What were the prospects for developing FMU-based agroforestry? How did agroforestry systems contribute to food security?

The results of this study were expected to contribute to the community regarding the management of candlenut-based agroforestry systems in an effort to support food security for communities around the forest. As an additional reference in conducting further research related to the management of agroforestry systems. Contribution of thought to the government in making decisions in relation to the use of forest areas in efforts to program food security in Central Sulawesi.

on banana peel Goroho nutritional quality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location and Time Research

This research was conducted at KPH Dolago Tanggunung Resort Sigi. The selection of research locations was carried out purporatively with the consideration that the community characterized a mixed garden farming system (agroforestry) which was focused on land use systems.

This research was conducted for 6 effective months, from April to October 2018, which included preparation, data collection (primary and secondary). For data processing activities, data analysis, to the preparation of a dissertation carried out from November to December 2018.

Research Object

The object of this research was agroforestry systems, which characterize both simple agroforestry systems and complex agroforestry in KPH Dolago Tanggunung Resort Sigi.

Table 1. Types of Agroforestry Plants Cultivated in Village Plots.

No.	Village Plots	Type of Agroforestry Crops and Plant Distance (m)	Wide Area (ha)	Population (trees)
1	Sigimpu	Candlenut 10x10, Cocoa 3x3 dan Vegetables	1	Candlenut 100, Cocoa 1.111
2	Bakubakulu	Candlenut 10x50, Durian 5, Avocado 10x50, Aren 30, Cocoa 5x4 dan Vegetables	1	Candlenut 20, Durian 5, Avocado 20, Aren 30, Cocoa 500
3	Bobo	Candlenut 10x10, Durian 7, Cloves 8x9, Avocado 25, Cocoa 4x5 dan Vegetables	1	Candlenut 100, Durian 7, Cloves 138, Avocado 25, Cocoa 500 dan Vegetables
4	Petimbe	Candlenut 10x15, Cocoa 4x5, Rambutan 13, Langsat 10, Manggis 13 dan Vegetables	1	Candlenut 66, Cocoa 500, Rambutan 13, Langsat 10, Manggis 13
5	Berdikari	Candlenut 10x12, Cocoa 4x5, Rambutan 10, Langsat 7 dan Vegetables	1	Candlenut 83, Cocoa 500, Rambutan 10, Langsat 7

Materials and Tools

The material for this research was the main stand of candlenut with a combination of agoforestry plants such as durian, langsat, mangosteen, cocoa, horticulture, as a sample that was deliberately selected and meets the requirements to be the object of research.

The equipment used in this research are:

- Location map to get an overview of the research area and its surroundings.
- Questionnaires and forms for collecting information from respondents and other data sources from observations.
- Staples and number tapes to number the stand samples taken.
- Tape recorder, to record conversations with respondents.
- Clinometer Suunto brand, to measure tree slope and height.
- A measuring stick, to measure tree height. Fabric measuring tape, to measure the circumference so that it was found mathematically the diameter of a tree.
- GPS (Global Positioning System), to determine the coordinates of the research plot.
- Photo and video cameras were used to record activities and objects of observation, especially important objects that were selected and displayed in the results of this study.

Research Procedure

The research procedure was carried out in stages, namely:

- Research Preparation

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Preparation of the research was carried out with the orientation of the research location field, determining the location, making the research plot, determining the sample and taking the sample according to the proportion of the population.

b. Data collection

The type of research data collected includes primary data and secondary data, as follows:

1. Primary data, which was generated from research and direct observation on the object of research include:

a. Implementation of land management.

b. Controlled inputs include costs of seeds, fertilizers, medicines, labor and other means of production.

c. The amount of production of each plant.

d. Potential stands of candlenut, durian, langsat, mangosteen, cacao and horticulture.

e. Identify in detail the structure and types of plant combinations.

f. Identification of various forms of land use

2. Secondary data, namely data or information that had been presented in written form or documentation in the form of statistical data or research results obtained from related agencies / agencies or institutions for research purposes, including:

a. Village / district / district history and monographs.

b. The district statistics for the research area, such as: commodity prices of food crops, fruits, plantations, livestock, grasses and Candlenut stands.

c. The bio-geophysical condition of the area involves, inter alia: diversity of flora and fauna, climate concerning climate types and monthly and annual rainfall, topography and landforms, soil conditions or soil types, hydrology, including Watersheds.

d. Social, economic and cultural conditions of the people residing in the study area.

e. Historical Tracing of Changes in Land Use

f. Research results that were relevant to the area.

Data analysis

Tree Volume Calculation

The general model of diameter at breast height (d) was very important for estimating the wood stock of forest stands, as well as in inferring basic information for developing a forest growth model, and as a basic input in developing a forest management plan. A general model was developed to estimate total height (HT) based on (d)) and baseline area variables (Santiago-García et al., 2020).

a. Tree Height

The volume of the stand could be determined by measuring the tree's height using clinometers with the help of a measuring stick along the 4 meters which was placed vertically on the tree trunk (Ruchaemi, 2006). The tree height was calculated using the formula:

$$h = (P2-P0) / (P1-P0) \times Pt$$

Information :

h: Tree Height

P2: Scale reading in percent for treetops.

P1: The scale reading was in percent for the end of the stick.

P0: Scale reading in percent for the tree base.

Pt: The length of the stick was 4 meters.

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Figure 6. Determination of Tree Height Using a Clinometer.

b. Tree Diameter.

Diameter measurements were measured with a measuring tape at a height of 1.30 m. The formula for getting the diameter value uses:

$$d = K / \pi$$

Information:

d = tree diameter (cm)

K = circumference of tree (cm)

$\pi = 3.141592654$

c. Tree Volume Calculation

The volume of the tree was calculated using the following formula:

$$V = 1/2 \times \pi \times d^2 \times h \times f$$

Information:

V: Volume (m³)

π : 3.141592654

d: Tree diameter at breast height (cm)

h: Branch free height (m)

f: Tree form factor.

d. Total Volume (TV)

Estimates of the total volume of trees per hectare could use the formula (Whitmore, 1984) (Swaine, 1985) as follows:

$$TV = (1/2 \times \pi \times d^2 \times h \times f \times n) / 10,000$$

Information:

TV: Total Volume (m³)

π : 3.141592654

d: Tree diameter at breast height (cm)

h: Branch free height (m)

f: Tree form factor

n: Number of trees

Financial Analysis

Private businesses need knowledge of their financial condition. There were various methods and procedures for creating a financial and economic analysis system for a business. Analysis was focused on evaluating a specific group of methods for predicting the financial health of a business entity. The financial evaluation of an enterprise was divided into point methods, mathematical methods, statistics and networks. Individual methods had different levels of difficulty, especially the data variables analyzed and their potential application (Majdaková et al., 2020).

Based on the data obtained, then a financial analysis was carried out in accordance with the research objectives. Based on Kadariah (1987), the data analysis criteria used were calculated using the following calculation formula:

a. Payback Periods

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Payback Period was the period required to pay back (return) all costs that had been incurred in investing in a project.

$$PP = n1 + (n2-n1) [a1 / (a1 + a2)]$$

Information:

PP: Payback Periods (years)

n1: End of year Net Benefit was negative (year)

n2: The initial year after Net Benefit was positive (years)

A1: The final amount of Net Benefit was positively valued (Rp.)

A2: The initial amount after Net Benefit was positive (Rp.)

b. Net Benefit Cost Ratio (Net B / C R)

Net B / C was the ratio between the Present Value of a positive Net Benefit (+) and the Present Value of a negative Net Benefit.

The mathematical formula for Net B / C could be written as follows:

$$\text{Net B / C} =$$

Information :

Bt: net benefit at the time of operation in year t

Ct: net cost in operation in year t

Kt: investment at the beginning of year 0

n: economic age of operation time (rotation)

i: prevailing interest rate (discount rate)

If $\text{Net B / C} \geq 1$, then the project was declared to be able to continue or earn a profit, but if $\text{Net B / C} < 1$, then the project will not provide any profit and vice versa.

c. Net Present Value (NPV)

According to Lahjie (2004) NPV was a calculation method to determine the present value of the difference between profits and costs at a certain discount rate and could show an excess of benefits compared to costs incurred, with the following formulations:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^{(t=n)} (Bt-Ct) / (1 + i)^n$$

Information:

Bt: Benefit in year t

Ct: Costs in year t

I: The prevailing interest rate

n: The length of the time period.

If the $NPV \geq 0$ was obtained, the project could be accepted or continued and if the $NPV \leq 0$, then the project was not feasible to run.

d. Internal Rate of Return (IRR)

Internal Rate of Return (IRR) was a discount rate that could make the project's Net Present Value equal to zero ($NPV = 0$), or it could make the Benefit Cost Ratio equal to one ($B / C = 1$). The formula for project analysis, IRR could be written as follows:

Information:

i ' : lowest discount factor

i " : higher discount factor

NPV ' : Net Present Value Positive (+)

NPV " : Net Present Value Negative (-)

If the IRR was \geq the bank interest rate, then the project was feasible to run, whereas if the IRR $<$ the prevailing bank interest rate, the project was canceled.

e. Equivalent Annual Annuity (EAA)

Based on Kadariah (1987), Equivalent Annual Annuity (EAA) was used in determining the scale of land management business based on the average needs of the head of the family per year (5 people / head of household) with an average net income per year per hectare of equivalent value. The formula used in calculating the Equivalent Annual Annuity (EAA) is:

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$$EAA = NPV \times i / (1 - (1 + i)^{-n})$$

$$\text{Business Scale} = TR / EAA$$

Information:

i: interest rate

n: length of time period

TR: Total Revenue (Rp. Year-1)

EAA: Equivalent Annual Annuity (Rp.)

Minimum Acceptability Rate (MAR)

As a basis for standard indicators of financial criteria in this study, the real interest rate was 5%, namely the real interest formula (Lahjie, 2004).

$$r = (1 + R) / (1 + i) - 1$$

Information:

r: real interest

R: nominal interest (14%)

i: Inflation interest (9%)

3. Sensitivity Analysis

According to Kadariah (1987), in order to avoid uncertainty in future economic development, project analysis was often based on projections. Uncertainties that will occur in the future such as:

There was an increase in costs (operational costs).

There was a decrease in prices so that it will reduce profits.

Possibly due to the influence of natural factors such as drought, fire, which could reduce production so that profits could decrease.

The possibility of an error in the yield per hectare transaction that will be analyzed was if there was a change in the increase in costs and or a decrease in income.

Sensitivity analysis was used to determine the possibility that occurs from the results of the analysis if there was a change or error in the basics of calculating costs and revenues. Changes or errors will affect the NPV, Net B / C ratio and IRR. The basics used in sensitivity testing or sensitivity analysis are:

The simulation of a decrease in income was 10%, while other factors were considered constant.

The simulated increase in total costs was 10%, while other factors were considered constant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PRODUCTION POTENTIAL AND FINANCIAL ANALYSIS OF LEFT, CACAO AND HORTICULTURE

Valuation models could be built and used for the financial analysis of the feasibility of an investment project. An overview of the financial feasibility of the valuation method was presented, as well as a general valuation model, which could be used as a basis when building a new model. The risk analysis method was used because uncertainty could greatly influence the assessment of results. New optimization methods could be used to estimate project investment financing needs, as well as new methods to predict the optimal sales year for investment. A case study was used to illustrate the use of a model to assess financial viability. The modified NPV, IRR and BCR should be used to assess the financial viability of an investment project. The calculation of financial feasibility as a valuation model allows users to perform sensitivity analyzes, scenario analyzes and simulations to analyze the risks associated with investment projects (Björnsdóttir, 2010). Reliable yield predictions were essential for sustainable forest management, with forest quality management plans dependent on the reliability of growth predictions. and results (Varkouhi et al., 2017).

Details of Investments in Candlenut, Cocoa and Horticulture Plantations (Model I)

The cultivation of Candlenut, Cocoa and Horticulture which will be described in this section includes costs that had been incurred, cost predictions to the end of the cycle, estimated growth of Candlenut, Cocoa and horticulture, price of candlenut wood per cubic and cocoa per kg. The calculation of financial analysis describes the costs incurred as well as the predicted costs that had been incurred until the end of the cycle. These costs were classified into fixed costs and variable costs.

The details of these costs were described as follows.

1. Fixed cost

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Fixed costs were costs whose total amount was always constant and were not affected by the total volume of production produced. The components of fixed costs in hazelnut and cocoa were as follows:

a. Planning

Planning for this activity includes the creation of land boundaries, assuming the costs incurred were IDR 100,000 / ha, each hectare was considered the same.

b. property tax

Land and building tax financing in this concession from the first year of management to the end of the cycle was assumed to be IDR 80,000 / ha per year, for each hectare cultivated was considered the same.

c. Guard Hut / Building

Building guard huts / buildings was done at the beginning of planting. Not all respondents make huts to cultivate crops, because the planting location was close to where they live. The initial cost of the cottage used was the assumed average cost of IDR 5,000,000. This cottage could generally be used for 5 years, so every 5 years there will be renovations and repairs with a repair cost every 5 years of 10% from the previous year. In the 5th year of IDR 4,500,000, the 10th IDR 4,050,000, the 15th year of IDR 3,645,000, - and the end of the 20-year cycle of IDR 3,281,000.

d. Management Fee

The amount of management fee charged here was the same every year from the beginning of the activity to the end of the business cycle, which was IDR 4,000,000. The salary earned here was the basic salary outside the piece rate paid for each activity.

2. Variable Costs (Variable Costs)

Variable costs were costs whose total amount will change in proportion to changes in the volume of activity. The variable costs involved in operating this activity were different for each activity, with the breakdown of costs per hectare as follows:

a. Land preparation

This land preparation activity was to eradicate unwanted wild plants, shrubs, woody plants until clean by cutting and cutting down. In land preparation using a workforce of 12 people for 5 days, the costs required for land preparation were $\text{IDR } 80,000 \times 12 \text{ people} \times 5 \text{ days} = \text{IDR } 4,800,000 / \text{ha}$, each hectare was considered the same.

b. Procurement of seeds and transportation of seeds

The procurement of combination of Cocoa Candlenut seeds per hectare varies with the assumption that the price of candlenut seeds was IDR 10,000 / seed and IDR 5,000 / seed. Transport of seedlings of IDR 1,000 / seedlings from the nursery to the location near planting, then lift them again to the place where the planting hole is. This activity was carried out at the beginning of the planting year. So, the cost of seedlings with a spacing of 10 m \times 10 m was 100 seeds / ha, which was IDR 1,200,000. while the amount of seed transport costs IDR 1,333,000 and it was considered the same for each hectare. Embroidering the seeds as much as 20% from 100 seeds / ha of 20 seeds / ha, a total of 120 seeds / ha prepared.

c. Planting

Candlenut, cocoa and horticulture planting activities include making planting holes, planting seeds and applying fertilizers. This activity was carried out at the beginning of the management year, the amount of planting costs for candlenut was IDR 1,000 / seed, so the cost for planting was $\text{IDR } 1,000 \times 120 \text{ seeds} = \text{IDR } 120,000 / \text{ha}$, while the amount of cocoa planting costs was IDR 1,000, - / seed, so the cost for planting cocoa was $\text{IDR } 1,000 \times 1,333 \text{ seeds} = \text{IDR } 1,333,000, -$.

d. Maintenance

Maintenance activities in the form of weeding the plants against weeds and wild cocoa as well as pests and diseases. This maintenance activity was carried out during the process of planting to harvest, starting from the age of 1 year to 20 years, each requiring IDR 80,000 / HOK with a total annual maintenance cost of IDR 1,200,000.

e. Fertilize and fertilize

Fertilization was carried out at the beginning of planting until the end of the cycle with the aim of stimulating the growth of candlenut and cocoa pods. The cost of fertilization for a year was IDR 640,000, - (Rp. 80,000, - / HOK). The fertilization process was carried out twice a year. The fertilizers used were in the

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form of manure, SP36, NPK and urea fertilizer. The price of urea fertilizer was IDR 15,000 / kg, SP36 was IDR 3,000, -, NPK of IDR 4,500, - and manure of Rp 2,000 / kg.

f. Equipment

The types of equipment used were machetes, hoes, buckets, axes and saws. The useful life of these equipments was calculated with the assumption that once every five years, a change of equipment was carried out until the end of the operating cycle with a reduced value of 20%. The amount of equipment costs was assumed to be Rp 2,000,000; IDR 1,800,000; IDR 1,620,000; IDR 1,458,000; and the 20th year of IDR 1,321,000,-.

g. Harvesting

Harvesting activities include three things, namely harvesting from the cutting of candlenut wood, harvesting cocoa pods and horticulture. Harvesting of cocoa starts in the fourth year to the 20th year, while the hazelnut harvesting starts at the age of 4 to 20 years. The cost of harvesting each year was assumed to be IDR 100.000, - / HOK x 8 times = IDR 800,000, - / year. The total income from harvesting the hazelnut fruit was IDR 126,000,000 at the age of 4, 5 and 6 years, then IDR. 378,000,000, - until the age of 20 years at a price of IDR 7,000, - / kg. Revenue from harvesting cocoa pods aged 4 years was IDR 1,800,000, -, then until the end of the cycle of IDR 57,600,000, - / year with an assumed price of IDR 30,000 / kg. The yield of horticulture was 25% from the hazelnut wood harvest of IDR 85,000,000, -.

3. Production and Raising of Candlenut, Cocoa and Horticulture Stands

In theory, the increase in standing volume applies the law of decreasing yield (The Law of Diminishing Return), where the calculation of projected wood production at the end of the cycle must be done in a "time series" so that the shape of the production growth curve could be known.

The spacing for the combination of Cocoa Candlenut cultivation was 10 m × 10 m or 100 stems per hectare. The growth increment of candlenut combination of Cocoa and horticulture could be tabulated as follows:

Table 2. Production of Candlenut and Cocoa Stands.

Year	n	d	H	V	TPst	MAIst	CAIst
		Cm	m	M ³	M ³ /ha	M ³	M ³
2	95	10.0	5.0	0.028	2.68	1.34	
4	86	15.0	6.5	0.084	7.21	1.80	2.26
8	78	28.0	7.5	0.342	26.64	3.33	4.86
10	71	35.0	8.0	0.577	40.97	4.10	7.16
15	70	45.0	10.8	1.305	91.33	6.09	10.07
20	68	50.0	12.0	1.813	123.31	6.17	6.39
25	55	58.0	13.0	2.678	147.27	5.89	4.79

Source: Data processed, 2019

Information:

n: Number of trees per hectare

d: Diameter (cm)

H: Branch free height (m)

V: Volume (m³)

TPst: Total Production (m³ / ha)

MAIst: Mean Annual Increment standing stock (m³ / ha / yr)

CAIst: Current Annual Increment (m³ / ha / yr)

Based on Table 2 it could be seen that the combination of Cocoa Candlenut stands was estimated to be harvested at the age of 20 years and had a total volume of 123.31 m³/ ha and an increment of 6.17 m³/ ha / year with an average diameter of 50.0 cm and an average increase in diameter of 2.5 cm / year. The average increment graph could be seen in the image below.

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Figure 1. MAI and CAI Candlenut and Cocoa Stands

The average increment had increased from the age of 4 years to 15 years and the increment had intersected at the age of 20 years. Meanwhile, after the age of 20, MAI and CAI standing stock had decreased. From the graph above it could also be seen that the decrease in the stand population of Candlenut and Cocoa per hectare at each age was due to natural mortality. It was estimated that the cocoa combination candlenut stands reach the highest increment with a wood diameter of 50.0 cm in the 20 year old felling year with an average tree height of 13.0 m.

Table 3. Candlenut Financial Analysis in Palolo.

Tahun Ke	Cost	Benefit	Net Benefit	Akum. NB	Discounted Net Benefit			Net Present Value			Net B/C Ratio			IRR
					10%	40%	70%	10%	40%	70%	10%	40%	70%	
0	43740	0	-43740	-43740	-43740	-43740	-43740	-43740	-43740	-43740	0.00	0.00	0.00	-
1	23720	0	-23720	-67460	-21564	-16943	-13953	-65304	-60683	-57693	0.00	0.00	0.00	-
2	23762	0	-23762	-91222	-19638	-12123	-8222	-84942	-72806	-65915	0.00	0.00	0.00	-
3	23520	0	-23520	-114742	-17671	-8571	-4787	-102613	-81378	-70702	0.00	0.00	0.00	-
4	24320	144000	119680	4938	81743	31154	14329	-20870	-50224	-56373	0.80	0.38	0.20	1.5%
5	30620	183600	152980	157918	94989	28444	10774	74119	-21780	-45599	1.72	0.73	0.36	28.5%
6	22080	183600	161520	319438	91174	21452	6692	165293	-328	-38907	2.61	1.00	0.45	39.9%
7	22080	435600	413520	732958	212201	39228	10078	377494	38900	-28830	4.68	1.48	0.59	52.0%
8	22080	435600	413520	1146478	192910	28020	5928	570404	66920	-22902	6.56	1.82	0.68	57.3%
9	22080	435600	413520	1559998	175373	20014	3487	745777	86935	-19415	8.27	2.07	0.73	60.0%
10	27750	435600	407850	1967848	157244	14100	2023	903021	101035	-17391	9.80	2.24	0.75	61.4%
11	22080	435600	413520	2381368	144936	10211	1207	1047957	111246	-16185	11.21	2.37	0.77	62.2%
12	22080	435600	413520	2794888	131760	7294	710	1179717	118540	-15475	12.50	2.46	0.78	62.7%
13	22080	435600	413520	3208408	119782	5210	418	1299499	123750	-15058	13.66	2.52	0.79	63.0%
14	22080	435600	413520	3621928	108893	3721	246	1408392	127472	-14812	14.73	2.57	0.79	63.2%
15	114303	435600	321297	3943225	76916	2065	112	1485308	129537	-14700	15.47	2.59	0.79	63.3%
16	22080	429840	407760	4350985	88740	1872	84	1574048	131409	-14616	16.34	2.61	0.79	63.3%
17	22080	424656	402576	4753561	79648	1320	49	1653696	132729	-14567	17.12	2.63	0.79	63.3%
18	22080	419990	397910	5151471	71568	932	28	1725264	133661	-14539	17.81	2.64	0.79	63.4%
19	22080	415791	393711	5545183	64375	659	16	1789639	134320	-14523	18.44	2.65	0.79	63.4%
20	194075	837012	642937	6188120	95569	768	16	1885207	135089	-14507	19.37	2.66	0.79	63.4%

Financial Analysis and Business Scale of Cocoa Candlenut Combinations

Based on the cash flow of the cocoa combination Candlenut cultivation, a simple calculation could be made of business time period, profit (difference between benefits and costs) and the value of the discount factor (DF). This calculation could be seen in cash flow. The following was a financial analysis of the cocoa combination candlenut cultivation.

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Cash analysis for cocoa combination candlenut stands could be seen in the table after the following discussion. The table shows that the total cost for the overall 20-year combination of Candlenut Cocoa planting activities was IDR 780,170,000 and a gross income of IDR 6,958,889,000, so the business had a benefit (B / C Ratio) of 19.38 which means that the business venture was feasible to be developed.

Candlenut Wood Combination Cocoa was ready for harvest at the age of 20 years with a total volume of 123.31 m³ / ha. 90% of the total yield could be used while 10% was used as firewood. The cash flow of the Cocoa combination Candlenut plant business could produce a financial analysis where at an interest rate of 10% the Net Present Value (NPV) value of IDR 1,882,384,000 and a Net B / C Ratio of 19.38 at a 10% discount factor, this statement was strengthened by analysis of the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) model with a value of 63.4% (Table 3).

Candlenut Sensitivity Analysis for Combination of Cocoa and Horticulture

a. Sensitivity Analysis if Benefit Decreases by 10% and Fixed Cost

Based on the results of the sensitivity analysis, benefits decreased by 10% and fixed costs, where at an interest rate of 10% the Net Present Value (NPV) value of IDR 1,664,629,000 and a Net B / C Ratio of 17.25 at a 10% discount factor, this statement strengthened by the analysis of the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) model with a value of 60.2%.

b. Sensitivity Analysis if Cost Increases by 10% and Fixed Benefits

Based on the results of the sensitivity analysis, if costs increase by 10% and benefits were fixed, where at an interest rate of 10%, the Net Present Value (NPV) was IDR 1,852,868,000 and a Net B / C Ratio of 17.45 at a 10% discount factor, the statement This was reinforced by the analysis of the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) model with a value of 60.5%.

CONCLUSION

The cultivation of Model I plants was profitable (feasible) to cultivate because it had an IRR value higher than MAR 5% and a Net B / C Ratio higher than 1.

b. The optimum age I Models was achieved when the candlenut stands were 20 years old.

c. The highest annual average increment (MAI) was achieved by Model I of 6.17 m³ / ha / year and the total volume of standing stock was 123.31 m³ / ha, while the lowest MAI was achieved by Model II of 1.33 m³ / ha / year and the total volume was 26.56 m³ / ha / year.

d. The operations of Model I show positive NPV values, so it deserve to be continued.

f. The level of resilience of Model I could still with stand economic changes with an increase in costs by 10%, or a decrease in income by 10%.

g. The need for the interest rate that could be given so that it was feasible to cultivate Models I was 5% to 89%.

h. The income level of the community who operates an agroforestry system could improve the welfare and education level of the family.

i. The community empowerment program in the working area block of KPH Dolago Tanggunu Resort Palolo had not been optimally implemented even though there were laws to accommodate it.

j. The candlenut-based agroforestry development model had very high potential to be developed in the KPH Dolago Tanggunu Resort Palolo area, so that it could be used as an agroforestry model for FMU management.

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